

What in the... What Is a "Rational Agent"?

Abstract

The social so-called sciences do not have a universal definition of "rational agent", despite the fact that some, and arguably all of them, depend on the concept to function. It is a central concept within economics, political theory and game theory, among others. The social so-called sciences do not even have a universal definition of "social", however, so what else could be expected? Nevertheless, this complicates the matter, because if no universally accepted definition exists, any attempts to discuss it could be immediately dismissed by saying "that is not the right definition". This is precisely the phenomenon this short note addresses.

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Basic Standards

According to the "social" "sciences", a definition of a "rational agent" is: An agent who:

- has preferences,
- whose preferences are internally consistent, and
- who chooses actions that maximize expected utility given their beliefs.

The problem of this definition should be immediately obvious: What does this have to do with rationality? What is the "rational" part of the "rational agent"? How do we know that one's beliefs are internally consistent? Without rationality, how can we know what people even want in the first place? "What do people want?" is perhaps humanity's longest-standing philosophical question. It is so for a reason. People may say they want "happiness", "family", "peace" and so on, but what do these words actually mean in practice? Perhaps someone would say that people's behavior reveals their preferences, but if we take a concrete example: A person obeys a tyrant. There is more than one possible interpretation in such a situation:

- The person obeys for the sake of survival.
- The person obeys because they genuinely support the tyrant.
- The person obeys due to self-deception.

The person could also lie afterward when asked why they obeyed. Ultimately, the person could also rationalize, rather than intentionally lie about, the reason for their action. How is the correct interpretation decided? Without clear definitions, this phenomenon follows: Anyone could reinterpret or rationalize definitions mid-sentence based on convenience, indeed without necessarily even realizing it. One could pretend that behavior reveals preference, but which one? One could say it does not matter, but it does not matter by what standards? It is well-known that people tend to rationalize post hoc the reason for their actions, meaning that they come up with explanations after acting based on what sounds reasonable rather than on what they actually believe, since they may not even be aware of their own beliefs. How do "social" "scientists" account for rationalizations, not only for the people they claim to study, but also within their own models? By defining "rational agent" without rationality.

Why did "social" "scientists" decide to use the word "rational" without actually grounding their ideas in rationality? The most generous interpretation may seem to be honest mistake, however, that interpretation would require the "scientists" to have barely even heard of rationality, and then just choosing the word based on hearsay. That is neither generous nor reasonable. The most generous interpretation is of course intentional deception: using the image of rationality while ignoring its requirement. Some might say that intent is difficult to prove, but let us put it otherwise: What evidence is there that "social" "scientists" are interested in reality? Of course, now they might dismiss this as "polemical", however, science presupposes truth as motive. Some define science as "method of minimizing bias", but science has no procedure if the goal is not minimizing bias. Moral character is scientific integrity, and science has no procedure for lack of integrity. Again, science presupposes integrity.

How could one prove scientific integrity? Not dismissing rational grounding as "polemical" would be a good start. The requirement of rationality is foundation in what cannot be otherwise, or axioms. Science is the systematization of reality within a rational

framework. Without a rational framework, science becomes indistinguishable from religion. Some might say that “the results speak for themselves”, and looking at the current world and human history, I must agree. If the entire system is distorted, could the apparent usefulness of the models simply be usefulness within the distortion, rather than usefulness relative to reality? Someone might insist that consistent prediction means there is some connection to reality, but:

- Why would that be?
- And even if it were connected to reality, which one? What is the point of studying patterns without understanding what they are anchored in?

Someone might say that “we have to be pragmatic” or “operational”, but what part of this is pragmatic? The terms are “operationalized” for what? Pragmatic for whom?... Someone might say that “everyone knows social science is fake”, but if “everyone knows this”, then why does it guide society’s policies?